

Supplementary Table S1. Prevalence of neck pain aged 10–24 in 1990 and 2019 for both sexes and all locations, with EAPC from 1990 and 2019.

location	Cases_1990	Rates_1990	Cases_2019	Rates_2019	EAPC_CI
Afghanistan	21583.51(12 788.88 to 33496.27)	569.05(337. 18 to 883.13)	74613.3(441 80.8 to 115707.13)	574.07(339. 93 to 890.25)	-0.28(-0.53 to -0.03)
Albania	3963.39(232 5.59 to 6185.39)	398.67(233. 93 to 622.18)	2460.02(140 4.93 to 3898.33)	434.15(247. 95 to 687.99)	0.35(0.25 to 0.44)
Algeria	49047.62(29 044.48 to 75967.7)	574.68(340. 31 to 890.09)	58745.74(34 613.63 to 92306.65)	601.12(354. 19 to 944.53)	0.42(0.32 to 0.52)
American Samoa	123.38(73.9 9 to 195.44)	819.86(491. 64 to 1298.68)	138(83.43 to 217.84)	807.19(488. 02 to 1274.21)	-0.14(-0.25 to -0.03)
Andorra	235.8(151.3 9 to 360.65)	1940.99(124 6.19 to 2968.79)	244.63(156. 39 to 373.21)	1919.43(122 7.1 to 2928.32)	-0.13(-0.15 to -0.1)
Angola	10263.88(60 72.18 to 16019.91)	319.96(189. 29 to 499.4)	30256.96(17 940.42 to 47038.27)	314.25(186. 33 to 488.54)	-0.03(-0.06 to -0.01)
Antigua and Barbuda	61.4(35.57 to 96.01)	352.7(204.3 1 to 551.5)	73.75(42.25 to 115.91)	364.37(208. 76 to 572.67)	0.07(0.01 to 0.12)
Argentina	47056.21(28 509.34 to 72476.22)	539.84(327. 06 to 831.46)	60375.44(36 662.19 to 93904.02)	567.15(344. 39 to 882.11)	0.15(0.13 to 0.16)
Armenia	3513.05(204 8.37 to 5481.76)	403.32(235. 16 to 629.34)	2230.67(129 1.46 to 3505.45)	409.42(237. 04 to 643.4)	0.44(0.3 to 0.58)
Australia	16810.23(98 21.8 to 26210.28)	423.41(247. 39 to 660.17)	19109.99(11 155.53 to 29697.89)	420.87(245. 68 to 654.05)	0.02(-0.01 to 0.06)
Austria	32152.36(20 412.5 to 49394.26)	1978.72(125 6.23 to 3039.82)	27545.9(176 66.08 to 42089.86)	1945.65(124 7.81 to 2972.94)	0.01(-0.02 to 0.04)
Azerbaijan	8663.66(503 6.85 to 13527.3)	409.24(237. 92 to 638.97)	9140.46(527 4.94 to 14390.82)	414.72(239. 33 to 652.93)	0.37(0.24 to 0.5)
Bahamas	286.02(165. 37 to 447.48)	353.85(204. 58 to 553.59)	329.89(190. 84 to 516.05)	353.83(204. 69 to 553.51)	0(-0.06 to 0.05)
Bahrain	793.31(468. 46 to	612.87(361. 91 to	1492.23(879 .89 to	601.34(354. 57 to	0.14(0 to 0.29)

	1245.05)	961.86)	2347.85)	946.13)	
Bangladesh	136813.06(8 0505.28 to 212934.65)	388.78(228. 77 to 605.09)	184706.5(10 7695.16 to 287117.45)	407.6(237.6 6 to 633.6)	0.17(0.15 to 0.18)
Barbados	241.99(139. 4 to 379.26)	358.08(206. 27 to 561.19)	204.85(117. 95 to 320.93)	356.93(205. 52 to 559.19)	-0.03(-0.04 to -0.01)
Belarus	8989.28(523 2.66 to 13999.25)	405.44(236. 01 to 631.41)	5683.56(331 9.25 to 8870.34)	403.22(235. 48 to 629.3)	0.32(0.18 to 0.47)
Belgium	32946.02(21 469.57 to 50497.24)	1636.96(106 6.74 to 2509.01)	31333.21(20 287.81 to 47855.21)	1615.4(1045 .95 to 2467.2)	0.11(-0.04 to 0.25)
Belize	207.8(122.3 to 322.43)	332.32(195. 59 to 515.64)	448.57(261. 41 to 700.09)	348.05(202. 84 to 543.21)	0.14(0.13 to 0.15)
Benin	4538.13(266 9.41 to 6956.47)	314.55(185. 03 to 482.18)	13213.35(77 17.15 to 20426.8)	321.91(188. 01 to 497.65)	0.09(0.08 to 0.1)
Bermuda	46.3(26.51 to 72.78)	371.5(212.7 3 to 583.91)	32.93(19.1 to 51.45)	351.11(203. 66 to 548.59)	-0.13(-0.18 to -0.08)
Bhutan	851.64(499. 21 to 1330.21)	396.73(232. 56 to 619.67)	900.11(515. 45 to 1417.1)	420.57(240. 84 to 662.12)	0.36(0.32 to 0.4)
Bolivia (Plurinatio nal State of)	6637.63(391 1.83 to 10298.16)	331.58(195. 41 to 514.43)	11420.93(66 11.91 to 17839.12)	352.23(203. 92 to 550.17)	0.26(0.23 to 0.28)
Bosnia and Herzegovina	4852.73(279 8.76 to 7640.64)	415.4(239.5 8 to 654.06)	2436.09(139 4.4 to 3844.09)	428.51(245. 28 to 676.18)	0.23(0.16 to 0.31)
Botswana	1432.25(847 .57 to 2229.94)	317.57(187. 93 to 494.44)	2179.94(127 8.31 to 3465.21)	335.24(196. 58 to 532.89)	0.25(0.21 to 0.29)
Brazil	228894.69(1 35071.22 to 359535.84)	491.42(289. 99 to 771.9)	260635.99(1 52789.06 to 413083.61)	518.85(304. 16 to 822.33)	0.33(0.29 to 0.37)
Brunei Darussalam	340.18(200. 33 to 527.5)	446.51(262. 95 to 692.39)	493.86(289. 62 to 771.22)	459.91(269. 71 to 718.21)	0.1(0.08 to 0.13)
Bulgaria	7421.82(432 2.28 to 11583.62)	403.16(234. 79 to 629.23)	3863.21(225 9.33 to 6040)	401.13(234. 59 to 627.15)	0.12(-0.01 to 0.25)

Burkina Faso	9096.11(533 5.89 to 13933.94)	307.96(180. 65 to 471.75)	22941.61(13 470.02 to 35255.1)	317.57(186. 46 to 488.01)	0.12(0.1 to 0.14)
Burundi	5340(3162.2 to 8349.9)	318.66(188. 7 to 498.28)	12199.11(72 17.39 to 19027.62)	318.32(188. 33 to 496.5)	0.16(0.1 to 0.23)
Cabo Verde	368.75(215. 13 to 571.06)	323.4(188.6 8 to 500.83)	523.3(305.2 7 to 818.66)	340.17(198. 44 to 532.17)	0.41(0.33 to 0.5)
Cambodia	26790.19(16 137.92 to 41637.64)	837.19(504. 31 to 1301.17)	40698.81(24 462.64 to 63798.58)	889.54(534. 67 to 1394.43)	0.45(0.37 to 0.54)
Cameroon	10279.94(60 24.8 to 15819.89)	319.07(187 to 491.02)	31218.12(18 239.83 to 48204.29)	322.12(188. 2 to 497.38)	0.07(0.04 to 0.1)
Canada	46451.39(28 381.93 to 71074.95)	796.89(486. 9 to 1219.31)	50133.12(30 677.65 to 76724.67)	792.88(485. 18 to 1213.44)	0.09(0.05 to 0.13)
Central African Republic	2772.04(163 4.88 to 4372.42)	326.09(192. 32 to 514.36)	5697.55(336 5.94 to 8952.42)	325.54(192. 32 to 511.52)	-0.02(-0.03 to 0)
Chad	5756.08(338 6.84 to 8825.19)	315.54(185. 66 to 483.78)	16758.67(98 34.03 to 25594.91)	312.3(183.2 6 to 476.97)	-0.07(-0.08 to -0.06)
Chile	21361.06(12 946.29 to 33178.35)	568.68(344. 66 to 883.29)	21916.2(133 03.47 to 34189.44)	573.76(348. 28 to 895.07)	0.15(0.08 to 0.23)
China	3776074.47(2204034.01 to 6020518.39)	1042.95(608 .75 to 1662.87)	2333303.78(1377762.02 to 3650755.53)	1024.92(605 .19 to 1603.62)	0.24(0.06 to 0.42)
Colombia	35570.79(20 696.14 to 55528.57)	347.78(202. 35 to 542.91)	42761.57(24 553.13 to 67122.84)	361.69(207. 68 to 567.75)	0.13(0.08 to 0.18)
Comoros	489.35(289. 85 to 760.59)	317.69(188. 17 to 493.77)	712.84(419. 07 to 1128.2)	332.05(195. 21 to 525.53)	0.12(0.1 to 0.13)
Congo	2615.65(154 5.55 to 4086.95)	322.09(190. 32 to 503.27)	5015.26(296 4.73 to 7846.28)	321.03(189. 77 to 502.24)	0.01(-0.04 to 0.06)
Cook Islands	46.85(28.28 to 73.74)	799.19(482. 5 to 1257.86)	33.86(20.31 to 53.68)	818.13(490. 82 to 1297)	0(-0.03 to 0.03)
Costa Rica	3167.89(184	344(200.75	4044.35(232	361.62(208.	0.32(0.27

	8.73 to 4926.68)	to 534.99)	7.04 to 6351.79)	07 to 567.93)	to 0.36)
Côte d'Ivoire	12411.03(72 67.11 to 19278.38)	324.38(189. 93 to 503.86)	26184.05(15 299.23 to 40560.37)	324.38(189. 54 to 502.49)	0.03(-0.02 to 0.08)
Croatia	4229.16(245 5.98 to 6611.52)	409.56(237. 84 to 640.28)	2854.65(163 9.22 to 4497.1)	421.22(241. 88 to 663.57)	0.13(0.1 to 0.17)
Cuba	11670.28(66 30.29 to 18367.81)	377.47(214. 46 to 594.11)	7285.83(416 4.23 to 11453.11)	366.19(209. 3 to 575.64)	-0.09(-0.24 to 0.06)
Cyprus	3636.49(232 2.74 to 5536.53)	1912.34(122 1.47 to 2911.53)	4192.55(268 9.28 to 6390.8)	1938.14(124 3.21 to 2954.35)	0.13(0.1 to 0.15)
Czechia	9338.94(548 6.75 to 14520.68)	392.68(230. 71 to 610.56)	6000.79(351 9.88 to 9395.56)	394.77(231. 56 to 618.1)	0.07(-0.07 to 0.21)
Democratic People's Republic of Korea	47936.56(28 909.2 to 73448.98)	867.4(523.1 1 to 1329.05)	48540.5(292 06.02 to 74903.06)	882.89(531. 22 to 1362.39)	0.12(0 to 0.23)
Democratic Republic of the Congo	38526.6(227 84.4 to 60195.53)	320.76(189. 69 to 501.16)	93014.81(55 007.66 to 145262.89)	321.01(189. 84 to 501.32)	0.05(0.03 to 0.07)
Denmark	26927.22(17 064.76 to 41126.74)	2462.92(156 0.84 to 3761.69)	26040.08(16 617.92 to 39564.18)	2442.03(155 8.42 to 3710.31)	0.23(-0.08 to 0.54)
Djibouti	553.61(324. 65 to 876.33)	329.42(193. 18 to 521.45)	1077.19(631 .45 to 1708.55)	328.48(192. 55 to 521)	0.16(0.1 to 0.22)
Dominica	78.34(45.69 to 121.63)	342.54(199. 78 to 531.82)	58.16(33.58 to 90.8)	352.47(203. 48 to 550.26)	0.15(0.08 to 0.21)
Dominican Republic	8275.77(482 0.04 to 12919.84)	347.67(202. 49 to 542.77)	10354.82(59 69 to 16222.15)	357.11(205. 86 to 559.46)	0.09(0.05 to 0.14)
Ecuador	11021.43(64 57.95 to 17099.34)	337.85(197. 96 to 524.16)	17326.98(10 017.79 to 27077.24)	352.92(204. 04 to 551.51)	0.11(0.09 to 0.13)
Egypt	98308.1(582 02.4 to 152447.95)	572.87(339. 16 to 888.36)	166602.05(9 8414 to 260280.03)	586.57(346. 5 to 916.4)	0.22(0.14 to 0.3)
El Salvador	5927.59(348 7.92 to	333.41(196. 19 to	6364.91(365 8.28 to	362.3(208.2 4 to 569.61)	0.18(0.09 to 0.27)

	9209)	517.98)	10006.81)		
Equatorial Guinea	408.39(241.47 to 637.14)	318.8(188.5 to 497.37)	1739.49(102.1.46 to 2732.52)	327.88(192.54 to 515.06)	0.12(0.09 to 0.15)
Eritrea	3148.92(186.1.52 to 4900.72)	318.71(188.41 to 496.02)	7410.87(436.5.84 to 11697.72)	328.37(193.45 to 518.32)	0.08(0.07 to 0.1)
Estonia	1324.69(770.31 to 2064.9)	405.56(235.84 to 632.18)	790.5(462.4.9 to 1236.62)	400.13(234.1 to 625.94)	0.25(0.11 to 0.39)
Eswatini	869.78(514.46 to 1351.77)	316.01(186.92 to 491.13)	1217.5(715.56 to 1927.67)	332.42(195.37 to 526.32)	0.24(0.22 to 0.26)
Ethiopia	61058.9(355.12.83 to 96081.64)	372.19(216.47 to 585.68)	143324.27(8.3051.28 to 226621.39)	384.36(222.73 to 607.75)	0.13(0.11 to 0.15)
Fiji	1898.14(113.9.24 to 2995.18)	796.86(478.27 to 1257.41)	1919.52(115.0.69 to 3037.24)	813.07(487.41 to 1286.52)	0.18(0.13 to 0.23)
Finland	22277.24(15.774.64 to 30587.35)	2288.58(162.0.56 to 3142.29)	21445.15(13.811.82 to 31935.96)	2336.95(150.5.12 to 3480.17)	0.69(0.03 to 1.36)
France	195353.41(1.26648.76 to 294701.34)	1545.83(100.2.17 to 2331.96)	183770.36(1.19200.24 to 277896.97)	1520.92(986.52 to 2299.93)	-0.05(-0.06 to -0.04)
Gabon	989.17(584.24 to 1553.84)	324.59(191.71 to 509.88)	1782.88(104.7.54 to 2834.93)	335.34(197.03 to 533.22)	0.12(0.1 to 0.14)
Gambia	1008.82(589.63 to 1561.46)	321.89(188.14 to 498.22)	2496.26(145.3.92 to 3866.77)	325.53(189.6 to 504.25)	0.03(0.01 to 0.05)
Georgia	5210.98(303.2.26 to 8115.97)	405.71(236.08 to 631.89)	2549.83(147.9.38 to 3989.69)	406.68(235.95 to 636.33)	0.23(0.14 to 0.31)
Germany	293071.43(1.86292.35 to 449140.77)	1967.84(125.0.87 to 3015.77)	247716.34(1.58926.75 to 378323.34)	1938.71(124.3.81 to 2960.88)	0.02(-0.01 to 0.05)
Ghana	15142.63(88.56.19 to 23379.87)	321.18(187.84 to 495.89)	33065.71(19.432.46 to 51482.37)	332.92(195.66 to 518.35)	0.14(0.13 to 0.15)
Greece	49602.05(31.413.3 to 75011.46)	2117.09(134.0.77 to 3201.61)	32650.84(20.633.85 to 49133.33)	2105.23(133.0.41 to 3167.98)	0.11(-0.07 to 0.29)
Greenland	117.43(71.1.117.43 to 117.43)	849.62(514.849.62 to 849.62)	91.99(56.27.91.99 to 91.99)	800.43(489.800.43 to 800.43)	0.11(-0.06 to 0.11)

	7 to 183.65)	93 to 1328.77)	to 141.45)	65 to 1230.81)	to 0.28)
Grenada	87.79(51.54 to 136.23)	334.74(196. 49 to 519.41)	95.75(54.75 to 150.16)	366.96(209. 8 to 575.46)	0.3(0.24 to 0.35)
Guam	339.04(202. 91 to 541.81)	864.65(517. 49 to 1381.79)	346.06(207. 45 to 549.54)	829.52(497. 26 to 1317.25)	-0.11(-0.23 to 0)
Guatemala	8135.48(479 3.42 to 12607.29)	326.65(192. 46 to 506.2)	19975.4(115 44.76 to 31233.39)	353.68(204. 41 to 553.01)	0.26(0.22 to 0.3)
Guinea	5618.71(329 5.16 to 8650.57)	318.28(186. 66 to 490.03)	12908.57(75 73.68 to 19865.45)	317.9(186.5 2 to 489.23)	0.04(0.01 to 0.08)
Guinea-Bissau	1025.91(602 .46 to 1576.29)	317.46(186. 43 to 487.77)	2042.05(119 1.89 to 3168.85)	325.62(190. 06 to 505.3)	0.15(0.12 to 0.18)
Guyana	896.46(522. 25 to 1397.22)	345.74(201. 42 to 538.87)	814.12(466. 47 to 1276.15)	365.98(209. 69 to 573.68)	0.03(-0.12 to 0.18)
Haiti	6436.31(379 6.18 to 9991.15)	331.81(195. 7 to 515.07)	12614.24(73 60.71 to 19628.06)	343.05(200. 18 to 533.8)	0.22(0.17 to 0.27)
Honduras	4928.78(290 8.36 to 7626.68)	321.59(189. 76 to 497.62)	10982.59(63 78.83 to 17161.44)	350.11(203. 35 to 547.08)	0.29(0.28 to 0.3)
Hungary	9063.58(533 2.31 to 14116.91)	392.99(231. 2 to 612.09)	6189.81(357 8.81 to 9741.49)	413.96(239. 34 to 651.49)	0.12(0.02 to 0.21)
Iceland	1222.69(781 .7 to 1867.79)	1934.15(123 6.56 to 2954.61)	1313.7(838. 07 to 1996.81)	1930(1231.2 4 to 2933.57)	0.03(0.01 to 0.05)
India	1204061.71(712369.16 to 1881129.77)	466.9(276.2 3 to 729.44)	1932061.35(1130385.03 to 3015028.01)	486.26(284. 49 to 758.82)	0.18(0.16 to 0.21)
Indonesia	598125.13(3 58296.18 to 941958.93)	1005.64(602 .41 to 1583.73)	706214.12(4 21428.28 to 1107933.27)	1040.28(620 .78 to 1632.03)	0.07(0.02 to 0.11)
Iran (Islamic Republic of)	166454(9794 1.13 to 264222.72)	866.96(510. 12 to 1376.18)	161950.28(9 5362.7 to 256368.75)	920.02(541. 75 to 1456.4)	0.7(0.35 to 1.04)
Iraq	31488.69(18	553.18(328.	79916.74(47	605.27(356.	0.19(0.09

	716.76 to 49040.63)	81 to 861.53)	103.04 to 125851.58)	75 to 953.17)	to 0.28)
Ireland	18554.38(11 959.13 to 28322.99)	1905.18(122 7.97 to 2908.23)	18204.19(11 684.83 to 27796.98)	1908.61(122 5.09 to 2914.35)	0.01(-0.04 to 0.05)
Israel	25891.97(16 664.28 to 39503.12)	1903.29(122 4.97 to 2903.83)	41341.93(26 528.88 to 63021.95)	1908.81(122 4.87 to 2909.8)	-0.01(-0.02 to 0)
Italy	274074.44(1 72595.55 to 418682.18)	2189.34(137 8.71 to 3344.48)	185307.23(1 18052.6 to 281288.89)	2126.6(1354 .78 to 3228.09)	-0.13(-0.15 to -0.11)
Jamaica	2632.06(153 3.89 to 4099.73)	344.62(200. 83 to 536.78)	2710.9(1552 .14 to 4252.18)	366.26(209. 7 to 574.5)	0.22(0.16 to 0.28)
Japan	151504.11(8 9441.54 to 234745.52)	539.08(318. 25 to 835.27)	96565.21(56 783.28 to 150362.32)	545.53(320. 79 to 849.45)	-0.11(-0.16 to -0.06)
Jordan	7881.62(465 9.11 to 12298.29)	576.39(340. 72 to 899.38)	20737.27(12 243.27 to 32415.13)	585.26(345. 54 to 914.84)	0.04(0.01 to 0.08)
Kazakhstan	17287.83(10 157.11 to 26927.73)	395.77(232. 53 to 616.46)	15544.73(91 03.77 to 24355.85)	397.8(232.9 7 to 623.29)	0.33(0.2 to 0.45)
Kenya	29696.02(17 226.08 to 46701.88)	374.72(217. 37 to 589.3)	66513.17(38 415.7 to 105101.81)	387.94(224. 06 to 613.01)	0.1(0.06 to 0.13)
Kiribati	184.45(110. 72 to 292.29)	825.53(495. 55 to 1308.17)	278.24(167. 04 to 440.53)	802.8(481.9 5 to 1271.05)	0.13(0.02 to 0.23)
Kuwait	2368.05(137 4.5 to 3797.74)	499.67(290. 03 to 801.34)	4044.09(234 5.68 to 6485.96)	504.01(292. 34 to 808.33)	0.18(0.11 to 0.26)
Kyrgyzstan	5064.13(298 2.63 to 7885.39)	391.79(230. 75 to 610.05)	6893.78(400 8.69 to 10757.44)	406.23(236. 22 to 633.9)	0.32(0.24 to 0.41)
Lao People's Democratic Republic	10646.82(64 08.74 to 16535.5)	822.18(494. 9 to 1276.92)	18771.21(11 256.54 to 29467.86)	891.45(534. 58 to 1399.43)	0.33(0.29 to 0.37)
Latvia	2237.54(129 2.38 to 3515.21)	414.55(239. 44 to 651.26)	1092.32(640 .16 to 1710.42)	398.4(233.4 9 to 623.85)	0.23(0.07 to 0.4)
Lebanon	5403.73(319 7.81 to	575.96(340. 84 to 895.1)	6481.06(382 0.99 to	587.13(346. 15 to 919.7)	0.39(0.27 to 0.51)

	8397.97)		10152.08)		
Lesotho	1894.21(112 1.22 to 2945.64)	317.04(187. 66 to 493.02)	2198.03(128 8.7 to 3493.23)	336.96(197. 56 to 535.51)	0.3(0.25 to 0.35)
Liberia	1723.84(101 1.59 to 2635.56)	298.12(174. 94 to 455.79)	5136.21(299 6.7 to 7941.55)	323.58(188. 79 to 500.32)	0.2(0.1 to 0.3)
Libya	7960.64(472 5.54 to 12404.53)	556.7(330.4 6 to 867.46)	10662.74(62 78.26 to 16752.86)	616.08(362. 75 to 967.97)	0.32(0.25 to 0.39)
Lithuania	3389.69(195 9.03 to 5323.03)	414.23(239. 4 to 650.49)	1848.58(105 8.43 to 2919.88)	427.26(244. 63 to 674.87)	0.29(0.19 to 0.39)
Luxembourg	1418.51(905 .29 to 2172.51)	1963.49(125 3.09 to 3007.17)	2033.52(130 4.79 to 3100.82)	1940.72(124 5.25 to 2959.32)	-0.02(-0.04 to 0.01)
Madagascar	12197.06(72 19.02 to 18998.63)	318.49(188. 5 to 496.09)	28635.96(16 906.88 to 44979.13)	325.13(191. 96 to 510.7)	0.03(0.02 to 0.05)
Malawi	9842.92(581 3.41 to 15440.68)	322.5(190.4 8 to 505.91)	21107.72(12 519.38 to 32724.67)	317.63(188. 39 to 492.44)	-0.12(-0.17 to -0.06)
Malaysia	34342.18(21 509.32 to 50907.32)	638.29(399. 78 to 946.18)	60582.15(35 159.92 to 97295.65)	741.91(430. 58 to 1191.52)	0.41(0.36 to 0.46)
Maldives	600.29(361. 01 to 934.14)	838.09(504. 01 to 1304.19)	954.79(570. 69 to 1517.2)	939.05(561. 28 to 1492.19)	0.78(0.64 to 0.91)
Mali	8014.05(471 4.42 to 12301.12)	314.99(185. 3 to 483.5)	23289.14(13 660.05 to 35797.78)	319.17(187. 2 to 490.59)	0.02(0 to 0.04)
Malta	1553.61(999 .92 to 2375.81)	1899.01(122 2.22 to 2903.99)	1276.85(819 .1 to 1948.69)	1946.18(124 8.47 to 2970.19)	0.12(0.1 to 0.14)
Marshall Islands	113.57(68.7 8 to 176.02)	744.36(450. 84 to 1153.73)	130.73(78.7 2 to 205.83)	796.38(479. 55 to 1253.88)	0.32(0.23 to 0.4)
Mauritania	2043.28(119 5.51 to 3153.08)	321.08(187. 86 to 495.48)	4319.65(252 9.25 to 6651.38)	320.69(187. 77 to 493.8)	0(-0.02 to 0.01)
Mauritius	2867.25(172 7.19 to 4478.8)	880.16(530. 19 to 1374.85)	2480.45(148 3.79 to 3927.75)	923.89(552. 67 to 1462.97)	0.13(0.06 to 0.19)
Mexico	118432.5(69	406.95(239.	138723.51(8	425.09(249.	0.12(0.1 to

	812.03 to 185497.87)	88 to 637.39)	1341.82 to 218025.19)	26 to 668.09)	0.13)
Micronesia (Federated States of)	256.51(155. 22 to 396.94)	746.86(451. 95 to 1155.76)	258.35(155. 87 to 408.56)	808.53(487. 79 to 1278.63)	0.25(0.24 to 0.27)
Monaco	85.89(54.57 to 131.58)	1978.57(125 6.9 to 3030.92)	101.92(65.2 6 to 156.15)	1940.53(124 2.47 to 2973.09)	-0.04(-0.08 to 0)
Mongolia	2757.5(1623 .94 to 4292.3)	390.44(229. 94 to 607.76)	2942.42(171 7.83 to 4589.58)	403.35(235. 48 to 629.14)	0.37(0.26 to 0.48)
Montenegro	642.98(373. 68 to 1002.5)	405.84(235. 87 to 632.77)	497.62(286. 95 to 783.09)	415.26(239. 46 to 653.47)	0.11(0.08 to 0.14)
Morocco	47282.74(27 991.17 to 73510.27)	583.2(345.2 5 to 906.69)	55908.65(32 985.59 to 87960.42)	601.15(354. 67 to 945.78)	0.16(0.13 to 0.2)
Mozambique	12553.99(74 37.49 to 19474.54)	307.77(182. 34 to 477.44)	31489.28(18 628.46 to 49166.86)	318.84(188. 62 to 497.83)	0.02(-0.05 to 0.08)
Myanmar	110555.28(6 6366.69 to 172418.62)	862.03(517. 48 to 1344.4)	129364.3(77 530.2 to 202748.63)	884.97(530. 38 to 1386.98)	0.11(0.09 to 0.12)
Namibia	1540.9(909. 55 to 2415.05)	324.76(191. 7 to 509)	2436.38(143 0.46 to 3867.35)	333.85(196. 01 to 529.94)	0.13(0.1 to 0.15)
Nauru	23.97(14.42 to 37.69)	791.22(475. 79 to 1243.84)	26.76(16.12 to 42.23)	801.39(482. 65 to 1264.5)	0.06(0.03 to 0.09)
Nepal	22845.91(13 495.85 to 35503.1)	383.9(226.7 8 to 596.59)	38967.87(22 724.44 to 60685.85)	407.94(237. 9 to 635.3)	0.18(0.14 to 0.21)
Netherlands	58998.3(377 34.75 to 90052.88)	1800.96(115 1.87 to 2748.92)	53874.67(34 523.2 to 81819.41)	1774.58(113 7.16 to 2695.05)	-0.2(-0.47 to 0.08)
New Zealand	3871.14(211 4.03 to 6273.38)	459.92(251. 16 to 745.33)	3575.84(225 7.02 to 5361.8)	403.95(254. 97 to 605.7)	-0.56(-0.63 to -0.5)
Nicaragua	4278.99(252 0.66 to 6630.84)	326.88(192. 56 to 506.54)	6656.53(386 4.32 to 10382.71)	349.99(203. 18 to 545.91)	0.3(0.28 to 0.32)
Niger	7659.62(451 3.47 to 11707.85)	313.24(184. 58 to 478.8)	24118.1(141 65.25 to 36849.51)	312.82(183. 73 to 477.95)	-0.06(-0.1 to -0.01)

Nigeria	111192.85(6 5774.29 to 175092.02)	394.93(233. 62 to 621.89)	279170.57(1 62444.58 to 436916.07)	384.6(223.7 9 to 601.92)	-0.11(-0.14 to -0.08)
Niue	4.96(3 to 7.73)	773.04(468. 25 to 1204.72)	3.14(1.9 to 4.94)	797.99(481. 68 to 1255.12)	0.14(0.08 to 0.19)
North Macedonia	2105.02(122 3.8 to 3279.41)	405.53(235. 76 to 631.77)	1626.3(930. 85 to 2568.11)	426.79(244. 28 to 673.96)	0.27(0.24 to 0.31)
Northern Mariana Islands	112.84(66.7 3 to 180.42)	890.23(526. 41 to 1423.37)	90.77(54.54 to 144.25)	859.86(516. 7 to 1366.48)	-0.51(-0.82 to -0.21)
Norway	13480.35(84 79.33 to 20518.87)	1470.5(924. 97 to 2238.3)	14959.8(930 8.1 to 22844.49)	1523.61(948 to 2326.64)	-0.02(-0.32 to 0.29)
Oman	2956.81(176 4.18 to 4568.83)	538.73(321. 43 to 832.44)	6105.2(3555 .98 to 9706.94)	643.62(374. 88 to 1023.32)	0.91(0.81 to 1.01)
Pakistan	161124.62(9 5130.54 to 250469.7)	451.34(266. 48 to 701.61)	340459.27(2 00630.7 to 528772.8)	463.91(273. 38 to 720.5)	0.04(0.02 to 0.07)
Palau	38.91(23.34 to 61.57)	828.92(497. 35 to 1311.75)	29.19(17.48 to 46.28)	819.13(490. 33 to 1298.5)	-0.06(-0.11 to -0.02)
Palestine	3822.33(226 5.94 to 5920.93)	564.86(334. 86 to 874.99)	9441.26(557 7.55 to 14749.68)	586.42(346. 43 to 916.13)	0.22(0.15 to 0.29)
Panama	2612(1520.6 5 to 4068.28)	346.46(201. 7 to 539.62)	3772.11(218 4.52 to 5887.03)	351.85(203. 76 to 549.12)	0.01(-0.02 to 0.04)
Papua New Guinea	10396.83(62 50.66 to 16367.68)	794.57(477. 7 to 1250.89)	23796.15(14 251.91 to 37616.1)	815.45(488. 38 to 1289.03)	0.1(0.06 to 0.13)
Paraguay	4328.48(248 6.5 to 6689.65)	351.08(201. 68 to 542.6)	7257.86(408 7.46 to 11384.58)	371.99(209. 5 to 583.5)	0.32(0.28 to 0.35)
Peru	23942.76(14 001.3 to 37189.36)	340.27(198. 98 to 528.52)	30617.75(17 703.88 to 47763.92)	352.73(203. 96 to 550.27)	0.15(0.14 to 0.16)
Philippines	253721.05(1 51904.49 to 393973.61)	1236.71(740 .43 to 1920.35)	410594.55(2 44573.34 to 645221.49)	1280.83(762 .94 to 2012.74)	0.12(0.09 to 0.16)
Poland	39712.29(23 405.43 to	462.26(272. 44 to	29043.55(16 901.47 to	494.81(287. 95 to	0.42(0.31 to 0.54)

	61591.94)	716.94)	45534.46)	775.77)	
	48157.86(30	1931.14(123	32472.16(20	1945.37(124	
Portugal	904.6 to	9.28 to	775.6 to	4.64 to	-0.04(-0.06
	73764.09)	2957.96)	49715.38)	2978.39)	to -0.01)
	3377.94(197	343.89(200.	2424.99(139	360.13(206.	0.14(0.11
Puerto Rico	0.33 to	59 to	3.55 to	95 to 565.2)	to 0.17)
	5256.85)	535.17)	3805.89)		
	583.41(342.	589.05(345.	3386.77(194	664.07(382.	0.78(0.62
Qatar	3 to 915.89)	61 to	8.84 to	12 to	to 0.95)
		924.74)	5568.85)	1091.93)	
	59814.95(35	454.68(267	39771.78(23	474.82(275.	0.09(0.01
Republic of	125.48 to	to 707.31)	104.88 to	84 to	to 0.17)
Korea	93050.15)		62624.97)	747.65)	
	4030.51(237	391.7(230.6	2511.26(145	411.69(238.	0.43(0.31
Republic of	3.59 to	7 to 609.61)	6.15 to	72 to 646.3)	to 0.56)
Moldova	6272.86)		3942.28)		
	23933.57(13	405.07(235.	12497.52(73	401.39(234.	0(-0.09 to
Romania	918.93 to	57 to	03.41 to	57 to	0.09)
	37290.59)	631.13)	19534.51)	627.41)	
	150951.1(88	479.18(280.	108054.98(6	473.85(278.	0.29(0.08
Russian	518.41 to	99 to	3549.55 to	68 to	to 0.49)
Federation	235176.44)	746.55)	168828.43)	740.36)	
	7185.95(425	317.97(188.	13683.91(80	326.28(192.	0.18(0.1 to
Rwanda	2.31 to	16 to	77.75 to	61 to	0.26)
	11194.01)	495.33)	21529.14)	513.35)	
	43.36(25.3	342.02(199.	47.01(27.09	357.56(206.	0.2(0.18 to
Saint Kitts	to 67.38)	52 to	to 73.72)	07 to	0.23)
and Nevis		531.39)		560.67)	
	154.73(90.3	341.43(199.	144.1(82.52	364.93(208.	0.24(0.2 to
Saint Lucia	6 to 240.52)	39 to	to 226.61)	98 to 573.9)	0.28)
		530.74)			
Saint		336.99(197.		355.21(204.	0.15(0.12
Vincent and	126.13(73.8	38 to	95.96(55.33	82 to	to 0.17)
the	8 to 195.83)	523.22)	to 150)	555.27)	
Grenadines					
	455.62(276.	775.16(469.	532.01(322.	775.38(469.	-0.07(-0.1
Samoa	07 to	69 to	46 to	97 to	to -0.04)
	708.69)	1205.71)	826.91)	1205.17)	
	110.7(70.68	1972.31(125	118.98(76.0	1952.19(124	-0.08(-0.1
San Marino	to 169.48)	9.28 to	6 to 181.89)	7.99 to	to -0.06)
		3019.65)		2984.43)	
	126(74.12	311.46(183.	218.01(127.	322.91(188.	0.15(0.1 to
Sao Tome and	to 192.73)	22 to	37 to	65 to	0.2)
Principe		476.42)	336.34)	498.18)	

Saudi Arabia	28988.63(17 147.61 to 45215.7) 7672(4505.3	569.97(337. 16 to 889.03) 317.17(186.	53084.68(31 310 to 84146.4) 16175.32(94	641.18(378. 17 to 1016.35) 323.45(188.	0.5(0.46 to 0.54) 0.08(0.05 to 0.1)
Senegal	9 to 11788.42) 8334.16(489	26 to 487.35) 397.93(233.	42.18 to 24982.65) 6481.16(375	81 to 499.56) 412.54(239.	0.09(0.05 to 0.13)
Serbia	3.53 to 12990.08) 196.48(117.	65 to 620.23) 880.06(527.	5.08 to 10172.57) 192.68(115.	02 to 647.5) 903.74(542.	0.16(0.13 to 0.18)
Seychelles	83 to 307.51) 3473.3(2026	78 to 1377.37) 324.34(189.	69 to 303.53) 9058.69(529	64 to 1423.68) 329.43(192.	0.13(0.09 to 0.18)
Sierra Leone	.79 to 5392.95) 3928.76(228	26 to 503.6) 476.42(276.	1.72 to 14097.47) 3528.9(2065	44 to 512.67) 470.27(275.	0.1(0 to 0.2)
Singapore	3.42 to 6199.19) 4990.96(293	9 to 751.74) 392.03(230.	.83 to 5543.69) 3490.97(201	3 to 738.76) 415.06(239.	0.3(0.21 to 0.39)
Slovakia	9.05 to 7779.88) 1814.56(105	86 to 611.1) 409.62(237.	4.32 to 5499.09) 1187.93(689	49 to 653.81) 408.71(237.	0.11(0.02 to 0.21)
Slovenia	3.53 to 2838.7) 892.79(541.	82 to 640.81) 772.91(468.	.07 to 1859.46) 1598.74(963	08 to 639.75) 788.53(475.	0.02(-0.01 to 0.05)
Solomon Islands	02 to 1389.14) 6782.45(399	37 to 1202.6) 296.06(174.	.62 to 2506.13) 21928.56(12	28 to 1236.08) 320.15(189.	0.04(-0.09 to 0.17)
Somalia	7.61 to 10545.41) 47155.68(27	5 to 460.32) 395.41(229.	954.78 to 34135.86) 56574.53(32	14 to 498.38) 403.37(234.	0.21(0.15 to 0.27)
South Africa	315.46 to 74598.19) 6477.38(381	04 to 625.52) 323.85(190.	821.13 to 90374.43) 10100.39(59	01 to 644.35) 312.39(185.	-0.21(-0.26 to -0.16)
South Sudan	9.77 to 10158.78) 145016.15(9	98 to 507.91) 1488.8(947.	85.2 to 15744.4) 101759.28(6	11 to 486.95) 1472.3(939.	-0.39(-0.79 to 0.01)
Spain	2296.51 to 223199.56) 45135.38(27	55 to 2291.46) 870.81(523.	4954.18 to 156268.08) 45153.57(27	78 to 2260.95) 875.85(525.	0.04(-0.02 to 0.1)
Sri Lanka	108.64 to 70439.58) 36738.38(21	02 to 1359.02) 569.36(337.	074.73 to 70608.43) 77716.33(45	17 to 1369.6) 577.82(341.	0.06(0.04 to 0.07)
Sudan	794.04 to	76 to	984.27 to	89 to	

	56722.77)	879.07)	120672.49)	897.19)	
Suriname	426.31(246.27 to 665.2)	353.49(204.21 to 551.58)	494.34(287.44 to 770.19)	347.87(202.27 to 541.98)	0.01(-0.03 to 0.05)
Sweden	39026.69(24883.87 to 60022.14)	2357.41(1503.11 to 3625.64)	39600.33(25486.07 to 60704.64)	2292.31(1475.29 to 3513.96)	0.24(-0.23 to 0.7)
Switzerland	26128.42(16638.54 to 40036.64)	1965.12(1251.39 to 3011.17)	26241.63(16886.94 to 39987.5)	1937.72(1246.96 to 2952.74)	0.01(-0.01 to 0.04)
Syrian Arab Republic	24174.24(14358.26 to 37657.33)	554.59(329.4 to 863.91)	28725.59(16937.66 to 44599.45)	588.91(347.24 to 914.34)	-0.03(-0.2 to 0.13)
Taiwan (Province of China)	49076.32(29690.15 to 76209.18)	858.33(519.27 to 1332.88)	30678.29(23071.35 to 40261.18)	812.92(611.35 to 1066.85)	-0.25(-0.39 to -0.1)
Tajikistan	6493.36(3823.86 to 10101.96)	391.61(230.61 to 609.24)	10911.15(6353.18 to 17012.22)	404.38(235.46 to 630.49)	0.3(0.21 to 0.39)
Thailand	160211.04(96174.95 to 251675.22)	895.81(537.76 to 1407.23)	123080.27(73498.45 to 195082.85)	937.88(560.07 to 1486.55)	0.1(0.06 to 0.15)
Timor-Leste	2021.7(1216.77 to 3160.45)	878.69(528.85 to 1373.63)	3910.33(2339.85 to 6114.34)	857.25(512.96 to 1340.43)	-0.08(-0.14 to -0.02)
Togo	3784.63(2221.98 to 5817.44)	317.32(186.3 to 487.76)	7961.42(4648.34 to 12302.71)	322.43(188.26 to 498.25)	0.07(0.05 to 0.09)
Tokelau	3.54(2.15 to 5.5)	764.95(464.24 to 1186.47)	2.88(1.73 to 4.55)	799.49(480.42 to 1262.13)	0.09(0.03 to 0.14)
Tonga	258.62(156.71 to 401.64)	773.09(468.44 to 1200.62)	243.14(146.96 to 381.47)	788.75(476.75 to 1237.51)	0.02(0 to 0.04)
Trinidad and Tobago	1172.12(684.71 to 1819.81)	341.32(199.39 to 529.94)	952.94(553.32 to 1486.12)	349.95(203.2 to 545.75)	0.33(0.2 to 0.47)
Tunisia	15645.29(9252.58 to 24383.21)	585.26(346.12 to 912.12)	14949.02(8814.08 to 23539.28)	601.94(354.91 to 947.84)	0.31(0.22 to 0.39)
Türkiye	109928.98(65076.23 to 170656.08)	578.67(342.56 to 898.34)	119858.03(70449.53 to 189223.87)	629.9(370.24 to 994.45)	0.21(0.16 to 0.25)
Turkmenista	4514.43(265	393(231.32	5057.57(294	403.26(235.	0.26(0.19

n	7.24 to 7025.68)	to 611.61)	9.71 to 7896.97)	19 to 629.66)	to 0.33)
Tuvalu	20.11(12.07 to 31.88)	819.03(491. 42 to 1298.24)	27.88(16.74 to 44.07)	815.3(489.6 1 to 1288.48)	0.05(0 to 0.11)
Uganda	18149.19(10 733.77 to 28375.52)	321.04(189. 87 to 501.93)	45913.06(27 184.08 to 71470.42)	318.86(188. 79 to 496.35)	-0.03(-0.05 to -0.01)
Ukraine	52189.51(30 601.54 to 81278.33)	481.56(282. 36 to 749.96)	31978.4(186 24.8 to 49865.49)	484.52(282. 19 to 755.54)	0.33(0.18 to 0.48)
United Arab Emirates	2546.85(150 1.83 to 4003.91)	603.83(356. 07 to 949.29)	6121.4(3627 .92 to 9521.49)	577.93(342. 52 to 898.94)	0.05(-0.26 to 0.36)
United Kingdom	225346.72(1 43997 to 341515.52)	1903.95(121 6.63 to 2885.46)	292899.79(1 88059.21 to 444062.19)	2487.3(1597 to 3770.97)	0.31(0.08 to 0.54)
United Republic of Tanzania	27101.29(16 034.84 to 42222.46)	318.21(188. 27 to 495.75)	59046.77(34 913.97 to 92397.44)	321.86(190. 31 to 503.65)	-0.01(-0.03 to 0.01)
United States of America	690145.21(4 19926.56 to 1057775.08)	1252.32(761 .99 to 1919.41)	1319629.6(9 24290.05 to 1829345.23)	2041.66(143 0.01 to 2830.27)	-0.37(-1.75 to 1.03)
United States Virgin Islands	93.88(55.11 to 145.52)	334.03(196. 09 to 517.79)	65.76(38.34 to 102.26)	343.2(200.1 to 533.7)	0.17(0.13 to 0.21)
Uruguay	4202.46(255 4.93 to 6469.7)	548.33(333. 36 to 844.16)	4246.28(257 7.13 to 6624.68)	571.26(346. 71 to 891.24)	0.09(0.07 to 0.12)
Uzbekistan	25117.25(14 785.28 to 39071.46)	393(231.34 to 611.34)	36361.42(21 120.9 to 56688.66)	406.23(235. 96 to 633.33)	0.29(0.22 to 0.36)
Vanuatu	368.04(223. 27 to 576.18)	779.02(472. 59 to 1219.56)	709.98(426. 58 to 1118.52)	791.83(475. 76 to 1247.47)	0.11(0.09 to 0.13)
Venezuela (Bolivarian Republic of)	20414.76(11 933.97 to 31695.59)	340.55(199. 08 to 528.73)	23086.92(13 454.47 to 35943.47)	344.23(200. 61 to 535.93)	0.14(0.08 to 0.2)
Viet Nam	184749.05(1 10934.83 to 288338.87)	857.2(514.7 2 to 1337.84)	190489.35(1 14430.27 to 299466.52)	903.23(542. 59 to 1419.96)	0.43(0.34 to 0.52)
Yemen	22036.19(13	521.86(313.	56510.68(33	556.02(330.	0.35(0.25

	250.5 to 33885.56)	8 to 802.47)	558.82 to 88045.94)	19 to 866.3)	to 0.45)
Zambia	8892.97(526 6.51 to 13869.46)	320.69(189. 91 to 500.14)	20040.15(11 838.94 to 31491.51)	325.5(192.2 9 to 511.49)	0(-0.02 to 0.02)
Zimbabwe	11366.33(67 32.82 to 17646.33)	316.68(187. 58 to 491.64)	15927.04(94 07.6 to 24989.3)	325.16(192. 06 to 510.17)	0.07(0.02 to 0.12)
